

THE IMPORTANCE OF GRAMMAR IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792395>

Annotation: Grammar is sometimes considered to be unimportant in a language learning process because of boring lessons or methods. But grammar has a vital role in this study and it is a basic stage of the process. This paper focuses on the importance of grammar in language learning and argues that, it has a great connection with integrated skills.

Keywords: grammar, language, learner, successful, communication

Mark Hellyer

Jerome was a humourist rather than a linguist, but this extract perfectly illustrates how studying grammar rules doesn't result in being able to communicate effectively in a foreign language. Unfortunately, more than a hundred years after he made that observation, grammar is still the dominant component of most English courses.

The first reason relates to the fact that we remember different things in different ways. Neuroscientist Michael T. Ullman uses the terms declarative memory and procedural memory, but linguists over the last 60 years have made this distinction with terms such as memory and retention, or learning and acquisition. We use declarative memory to remember facts, like the capital of Portugal, or what we had for breakfast, or that the thing we use to eat soup with is a spoon. So it's declarative memory that we use for vocabulary, and it's a fairly easy process. Learning grammar, however, is much more complicated, rather like learning to play a musical instrument for example, and for that we use procedural memory. So mastering the grammar of a language is a slow subconscious process which happens over time when we are exposed to the language; the explicit study of grammar rules has little influence on it

The second reason is that with the exception of needing to pass an exam in the target language, grammatical perfection is not necessary for most learners to achieve their goal, which is to use the language to communicate effectively. As Michael Lewis stated in *The Lexical Approach* back in 1993: 'Ultimately, language is not about right or wrong but about successful or unsuccessful communication'. Poor pronunciation is actually far more likely to lead to a breakdown in communication than poor grammar.

The third reason is that when most people learn a language they do it primarily for oral communication. Why is this important? Well, because most grammatical descriptions of English are based on the written language, and writing and speaking are not the same thing at all. Now what does this mean exactly? Well, if you look at a transcript of natural spoken English you'll see that it is very untidy, especially when compared to a piece of written English. Most spoken discourse is composed in real time. Speakers are working out what they want to say and producing language at the same time. This is no simple task, and as a result there are several features which are common in spoken English, but unusual or non-existent in written English. I'm not going to go into these differences here because it would take too long. The point is this: a great deal of coursebook content and lesson time is given over to explaining the grammar rules of written English, when we know that grammar rules are very

difficult to consciously learn and apply when speaking, and that grammatically faultless sentences are not a realistic goal for most learners. [1]

For well over half a century now, there has been much debate among linguists and academics about the relevance of formal grammar to the teaching of the English language, whether for native speakers or for those learning English as a second or foreign language. There was indeed a time, in the late twentieth century, when formal grammar virtually fell out of the secondary school English syllabus in Britain and the USA. Teaching grammar was deemed elitist or superfluous. On the one hand Chomsky had proposed his theory of universal grammar, suggesting that childrens' brains were all wired up to understand grammar by intuition; on the other hand Chomskyian linguistics was considered - not without good reason - beyond the grasp of teenage learners and of many of their teachers too. So rejecting earlier prescriptive or structuralist approaches to grammar, many linguists concluded that it was best not to teach grammar at all. Teaching generative grammar, let alone transformational grammar, to learners would be elitist, since only the best school students or EFL learners would be able to follow.

Offering a fresh approach to traditional grammar, Andrew Rossiter's Descriptive Grammar of English is accessible to both teachers and students. Unlike the other main grammar reference books available today, this pedagogical grammar sets out to show how simple grammar is, not how complex it can be.

Most of today's English grammars have been written by linguists (experts in linguistics), and instead of explaining grammar for the needs of ordinary teachers and learners, their attention to detail and linguistic explanations often complicates rather than clarifies.[2]

Grammar is the sound, structure, and meaningful system of language. All languages have grammar, and every language has its own grammar. People who speak the same language are able to communicate because they intuitively know the grammatical system of that language that is, the rules of making meaning. Grammar is important because it is the language that makes it possible for us to talk about the language

Yes, grammar may seem easy to some and difficult to others. And they think it's easy. Or they give up because it is difficult. But grammar is very important to me. Nowadays, many people think that they can focus on speaking without learning grammar. Yes, they can speak, but they still make grammatical mistakes. Because without grammar, our sentences cannot be formed correctly. And our words will be short and simple. Even if we want to pass IELTS, we need grammar, which word is used where, especially in Writing and Speaking, it plays a very important role. Although grammar takes up a lot of our time, we learn to speak well and without fear.

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